

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF RECYCLED COARSE AGGREGATE IN CONCRETE

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Abstract

This research investigates the structural performance of concrete incorporating recycled coarse aggregate (RCA) through finite element analysis (FEA) with increasing emphasis on sustainable construction practices, RCA presents an eco-friendly alternative to natural aggregates. A numerical model was developed using SAP2000 to simulate the behavior of RCA concrete under compressive loading. Experimental results were used to calibrate and validate the model. The analysis revealed that RCA concrete exhibits slightly lower stiffness but comparable load-bearing capacity to natural aggregate concrete. The findings support the feasibility of RCA in structural applications, contributing to sustainable development in the construction industry.

Keywords: Recycled Coarse Aggregate, Finite Element Analysis, Sustainable Construction, SAP2000, Concrete Modeling

1. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry significantly contributes to environmental degradation through the extensive use of natural resources. Recycled coarse aggregate (RCA) derived from demolition waste offers a sustainable alternative, reducing the demand for natural aggregates and minimizing construction waste. This study focuses on understanding the mechanical behavior of RCA concrete through finite element analysis (FEA), aiming to validate its applicability in structural elements. Recycling of demolished concrete into aggregate is environmentally beneficial by preserving NA resources, by waste reduction and by preserving landfill space [2].

In construction involving RAC, there are many issues have been investigated; such examples include the mechanical properties related to the replacement ratio of RCA in mixtures the bond-interface between RAC and steel bars, the quality of coarse aggregate mixes durability, shrinkage, and beyond [4].

Figure 1 Aggregates taken from demolished structure

Aim

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the properties of concrete produced by using recycled aggregates (wastes from demolished structure), with a

focus on evaluating its workability, compressive strength, tensile strength, flexural strength, and density.

The objectives of the research reported in this paper were to assess the flexure, shear, and bond splitting strength of RAC structural elements, and to investigate the difference in strength and behavior between conventional and recycled aggregate structural concrete elements.[3]

Objective of Work

- To analyze the Stress-strain behavior of RCA.
- To evaluate the effect of Recycled coarse aggregate on the mechanical properties of concrete.
- To compare the properties of recycled coarse aggregates with natural coarse aggregates

Scope of work

It will help to reduce waste disposal by utilizing crushed tile waste. Improve the mechanical properties and durability of concrete. Provide a viable solution for the construction industry to reduce its environmental footprint.

Study Area

The main variables that affect the resistance of a reinforced concrete element are the concrete's compressive strength, the concrete's tensile strength, the yield strength of the rebars, the dimensions of the cross sections and the eccentricity of the rebar's [5].

We could also analyze the environmental and economic benefits, such as waste recycling, reduction in natural resource depletion, and cost-effectiveness. This study could be situated within the broader context of sustainable construction practices, aiming to contribute to eco-friendly building materials and waste management solutions in the construction industry.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous studies have demonstrated varying mechanical properties of RCA concrete, including reduced compressive strength and modulus of elasticity. However, modern techniques such as FEA allow for detailed internal stress analysis and failure prediction, enhancing our understanding of RCA's structural potential. Research has also shown the effectiveness of the Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model in simulating concrete behavior under various loading conditions.

3. METHODOLOGY

Concrete specimens with varying RCA replacement levels (0%, 20%, 40% and 60%) were cast and tested under uniaxial compressive loading. The finite element model was constructed using SAP2000, with concrete modelled as a nonlinear isotropic material incorporating stress-strain data derived from experimental tests. RCA-specific properties, such as reduced modulus of elasticity and increased porosity, were integrated into the material definitions. Load application and support conditions replicated the experimental configuration. A convergence study was performed to ensure mesh sensitivity did not significantly affect the accuracy of the results.

Materials

- Cement: Use Ordinary Portland Cement (OPC-43) conforming to relevant standards (e.g., ASTM or IS specifications).
- Fine Aggregate: Natural sand meeting grading requirements.
- Coarse Aggregate: Conventional coarse aggregate (e.g., crushed stone) as the control material.
- Recycled Coarse Aggregate: waste aggregates from demolished construction material (e.g., 10-20 mm) using a sieve to ensure uniformity.
- Water: Potable water for mixing and curing.
- Admixture: Silica Powder.
- Properties of Silica: Silica, especially in the form of silicon dioxide (SiO₂), plays a critical role in concrete both in its natural form (in aggregates) and as an additive like silica fume.
- Enhances strength by reacting with calcium hydroxide to form more C-S-H gel.
- Reduces permeability and chloride ion ingress (less corrosion risk).
- Silica fume reduces bleeding

Table 1 Comparison of Properties of NCA & RCA

Table Properties	Natural Aggregates	Recycled Coarse Aggregates
Specific Gravity	2.6	2.2
Moisture Content	1.2%	2%
Water Absorption	0.7%	3.5%
Bulk Density	1.6 g/cm ³	1.4 g/cm ³

Test Required

- Compressive Strength Test
- Tensile strength Test
- Modulus of Elasticity
- Poisson's ratio

4. RESULT

Some relative experiments were carried out with cube (150×150×150 mm) specimens to examine the simulation's accuracy. The FEA results showed good agreement with experimental data. While RCA concrete displayed reduced stiffness, its peak load capacity was within acceptable limits for structural applications. Stress distribution patterns indicated more uniform cracking in RCA mixes, attributed to weaker interfacial transition zones. The validated FEA model provided insights into failure mechanisms and can be used to optimize mix design.

Table 2 Experimental Results after 28 days of Curing

RCA %	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Modulus of Elasticity (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Poisson's Ratio
0% (NCA)	32.5	31.0	3.8	0.22
20% RCA	30.0	29.5	3.5	0.23
40% RCA	27.5	28.0	3.2	0.24
60% RCA	25.0	26.5	2.9	0.25

Table 3 Comparative Analysis of NCA & RCA

Criteria	0% (NCA)	20% RCA	40% RCA	60% RCA
Load Capacity (kN)	750	700	640	580
Stiffness (Initial Slope)	High	Slightly lower	Moderate drop	Noticeable drop
Cracking Behaviour	Vertical	Vertical	Diagonal + vertical	Mixed (shear + crushing)
Failure Ductility	Moderate	Slightly higher	Higher	Highest

Figure 2 Graph showing Stress-Strain Behavior of RCA

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms that RCA can be effectively used in concrete for structural applications, with minor

compromises in mechanical performance. FEA proves to be a valuable tool in assessing and optimizing the use of RCA. Future work should explore the long-term durability and environmental impact of RCA concrete, as well as its behavior under dynamic and cyclic loading conditions.

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